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Representation of Sports Culture in *The Sun Also Rises*

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Abstract:

In the world, a number of countries laid prominence on a specific sport based on their social, cultural and historical aspects. Sports denote the culture of a country and its values. Sports embrace a sacred place. The writers like Joyce Carol Oates, David Foster Wallace, Ernest Hemingway, and Henry Fielding provide account of Sports and games in their writings. The entire world has a sports culture based on the religion and particular customs of the country. *The Sun also Rises* is one of the unique works of Hemingway. Hemingway's visits to Spain made him contribute the experience of sports, the traditional world of festivities and customs, elaborately. The sport of fish hunt is very well-liked in Spain and Portugal. It is a part of ethnicity in Spain. It represents the sporting way of life of the natives. The passion for Bullfight is widespread among youth like Jake, Bill and Mike. Youth often talk about Bulls and bull fighters. And those who are not ardent are not honoured. People arrive from distant towns at the time of Fiesta and enjoy watching Bull fights. The marvelous celebrations of fiesta show the cultural tradition of the people of Pamplonia. Author's indepth description of the fiesta reveals the ardor and enthusiasm of the people toward the sport of bull fight. Hemingway's sportive nature also reflects in *The Sun Also Rises*. His annotations on sports, his aptitude of portrayal and his energy are a source of stimulation for the readers. Sports culture keeps humans physically as well as spiritually strong and vigorous.

Keywords: Sports, culture, tradition, religion and youth.

In the world, several countries show importance for a specific sport based on their societal, cultural and historical aspects. The sports such as baseball in the U.S., football in Australia cricket and hockey in India, soccer in Brazil, badminton in China, and cricket in England are known as national games. Besides, the traditional sports are also sponsored in the nations. In India, kabaddi and kho-kho are traditional sports. Sports imply the culture of a country and its values. Sports culture is considered as “A combination of expecting beliefs and assumptions in sports., behaving in ways in accord with favored social values and norms, including respectful behaviours, observing ethics, and the adoration of other nation’s cultures:., creating sport participating habits through managing resources in order to make circumstances and tools for sport activities more readily available to those who fancy to participate in sports: and presenting the artistic and aesthetic aspects of sports as considerable cultural artifacts in society” (Keshar Sara) .

Sports hold a consecrated place in every culture, particularly in western culture. The writers like Joyce Carol Oates, David Foster Wallace, and Henry Fielding give account of sports and games in their writings. Through their oral craftsmanship, the writers investigate the complexities of life of youth and old people, analogous to that of sports persons. Sports are a social, collective, and cultural activity which brings all citizens mutually without any prejudice. Sports culture thus helps people retain harmony in relations and contributes in the health and wellness of people. Pierre de Courtin- ‘ father’ of the modern Olympic games, believed that sports events are very important tools for the backing of human rights. Pierre asserted, “ Sports should have the explicit function to encourage active peace, international understanding in a spirit of mutual understanding in a spirit of mutual respect between people from different origins, Ideologies and creeds.” Involvement in any sport can promote human rights. They encourage and augment social and cultural life by bringing together people, villagers and communities. Moreover, sports help to subsiding cultural differences and bigotry. It is aptly said that “Practice of sport is a human right every individual must have the possibility of practicing sport without” (Olympic Charter). Eric Dunning, a British Sociologist in his notable book *Sport Matters*, interprets on sports and its relevance to the animals, human ethnicity: “Sports can also be said

form of non-scripted, largely non-verbal theatre, and emotional aroused can be enhanced by spectacular presentation, the emotional ‘contagion’ which derives from being part of a large, expectant crowd, and from the performances which spectators and not just athletes put on.” Sports, therefore, hold a significant role on man.

The entire world has sports culture based on the religion and particular customs of the country. A lot of writings on sports in the form of Autobiographies, Biographies and memoirs are produced reflecting their own culture. “Sports Literature as a proper field developed in the late 19th century when literacy writers have started producing works that are centered on sports. In the hands of the writers like Ernest Hemingway, Novman Marler, C.L.R James, Tom Stoppard, David Foster Wallace, Ramachandra Guhe.” (kumar Vinoth 2022) Bruce Emra affirms “Sports in Literature features a variety of literary forms, presenting heroes and villains, the famous and the obscure and their triumphs and defeats as seen through the eyes of contemporary and classic writers” (Bruce Emra 1990).

The Sun also Rises is one of the inimitable works of Hemingway. Hemingway himself was an active sports person and he vividly gives representation of the sports such as bullfight and baseball. He uses all his skills as a close observer. He also recounts his own experience as sports personnel. Hemingway’s visits to Spain prepared him share the experience of sports, the traditional world of festivities and custom, magnificently. Sports culture is very common among humans. Some learn it for physical composition while some as a precondition. Robert Cohn, a middleweight boxing champion of Princeton, learnt boxing to thwart the feeling of inferiority and bashfulness; he had felt on being treated as Jew at Princeton. Robert Cohn had an inner attitude that he cannot knock down anyone who was better to him. But, he proves his boxing strength in the gym. Robert Cohn was a Jew by birth. Accordingly, he learnt boxing, despite the fact that it was very painful for him to become skilled at it. He learnt it to counteract the emotion of apprehension and trepidation on being treated as a Jew. Cohn learned it at Spider Kelly and was very prompt at boxing. Robert Cohn was an associate, through his father, one of the richest Jewish families in New York. At the military school, Cohn played a very excellent end on the football team, and no one had made him race cognizant, as a Jew. Cohn was an exceptionally timid boy and it made him bitter. He took it out in boxing.

Having divorced and bothered by the unhappy marriage, Robert Cohn moved to California and took the profession of editor for a magazine. He read numerous books, played tennis, bridge, and boxed at a local gymnasium. Cohn's love for Brett, perturb him mentally. Despite of his cheery and graceful personality, Cohn was not liked by Brett. His unreciprocated love makes him insipid and dull. Though he was good at tennis, he doesn't show any attention in tennis or any other sport. His healthy, vigorous, and adventurous spirit gets diminished on the love failure. "The sort of healthy conceit that he had, when he returned from America early in the spring was gone. Then he had been sure of his work, only with these personal longings for adventure. Now the sureness was gone. The reason is until he fell in love with Brett". (Hemingway 32)

Human psychology plays a significant role in keeping sportive spirit. If one is not healthy physically and mentally, he/ she will not accept the challenges either of life or of sports. In *The Sun Also Rises*, Robert Cohn's unrequited love makes him nervous and pathetic. His love for tennis also gets diminished as his love. Though he loved tennis, he develops dislike to the sport of tennis out of frustration in love. "He loved to win at tennis. He probably loved to win as much as Lenglen, for instance. On the other hand, he was not angry at being beaten: when he fell in love with Brett his tennis game went all to pieces."(Hemingway 32)

The sport of fish hunt is very popular and trendy in Spain and Portugal. It is a part of culture in Spain. It exemplifies the sporting culture of the natives. The anglers find it appealing to fish in the fresh waters. When Mike, Jake and Cohn reach Spain, they find the city clean and enjoyable. They are captivated by the big river on which the city was built. "In the morning, it was bright and they were sprinkling the streets of the town, and we all had breakfast in a cafe. Bayonne is a nice town. It is like a very clean Spanish town and it is on a big river. Already, so early in the morning, it was very hot on the bridge across the river. We walked out on the bridge and then took a walk through the town. "(Hemingway 65)

On seeing the pleasurable atmosphere of the river, Mike, Jake, Cohn and Bill hunt for rods as they prefer to hunt fishes in the river to keep them amused. Accordingly, they search in the city for fishing rods. On searching, they find and buy rods in a dry-goods store and landing nets

for each. “I was not at all sure Mike's rods would come from Scotland in time, so we hunted a tackle store and finally bought a rod for Bill upstairs over a dry-goods store. The man who sold the tackle was out, and we had to wait for him to come back. Finally he came in, and we bought a pretty good rod cheap, and two landing-nets”(Hemingway 65).

The two friends Bill and Jake start their delight journey on the road; move across meadows, fields and up the hills. They cross a stream on a foot-log. Beyond the streams, they cross another quickly flowing streams. After a long walk, they move from woods and forest towards the river-valley. They stop under some trees beside a dam that crossed the river. Bill and Jake were fascinated and engage themselves in fishing. Bill and Jake joint up the rods tie on leaders and get ready to fish. Bill fastens bait of worm for fishing. The conversation between Bill and Jake, typify their gusto for the sport like fishing, as they find it refreshing. Their temptation to fish in a valley reveals their sportive nature:

“The road came out from the shadow of the woods into the hot sun. Ahead was a river valley. Beyond the river was a steep hill. There was a field of buck wheat on the hill. We saw a white house under some trees beside a dam that crossed the river.

Bill put the pack against one of the trees and we jointed up the rods, put on the reels, tied on leaders, and got ready to fish.

“you are sure thing thing has trout in it?” Bill asked.

“It's full of them.”

“You going to to fish bait”?

“Yeah. I'm going to fish the dam here.”

“Well, I'll take the fly--book, then. “ He tied on a fly”Where'd I better go? Up or down?.

Down is the best. They're plenty up above too. “

Bill went down the bank.

“Take a worm can”

“No, I don't want one. If they won't take a fly I'll just flick it around. “

Bill was down below watching the stream” (Hemingway 87).

Bill and Jake's sportive nature keeps them active and happy for sometime without any conditions about life. A detailed account of Bill and Jake's fishing keeps reader also engaging: “I

got my rod that was leaning against the tree, took the bait-can and landing-net, and walked out on to the dam.... As I baited up, a trout shot up out of the white water into the falls and was carried down. Before I could finish baiting, another trout jumped at the falls, making the same lovely arc and disappearing into the water that was thundering down. I put on a good-sized sinker and dropped into the white water close to the edge of the timbers of the dam. I did not feel the first trout strike. He was a good trout, and I banged his head against the timber so that he quivered out straight and then slipped him into my bag.” (Hemingway 87).

On fishing, Bill and Jake find themselves refreshing. Jake succeeds in fishing six trouts. He looks at the trouts with great admiration, approves of the beautiful colours of the trouts and covers them with ferns. “While I had him on, several trout jumped at the falls. As soon as I baited up and dropped in again, I hooked another and brought him in the same way. I laid them out, side by side, all their heads pointing the same way, and looked at them. They were beautifully coloured and firm and hard from the cold water. It was a hot day, so I slit them all and shucked out the insides, gills and all, and tossed them over across the river. I took the trout ashore, washed them in the cold, smoothly heavy water above the dam, and picked some ferns and packed them all in a bag, three trout on a layer of ferns, then another layer of ferns, then three more trout, and then covered them with ferns. They looked nice in the ferns, and now the bag was bulky and I put it on in the shade of the tree” (Hemingway 88).

People enjoy Sports as they find it challenging. Bill too celebrates fishing. He baits big trouts compared to Jake. He makes fun of Jake on learning that he fished the small ones. Bill and Jake stay for five days at Briquette and go for good fishing. They join the company of an Englishman named Harris, who connects them to the Irati River for fishing. The conversation between Bill and Jake affirm the culture of fishing in Spain. “I only thought if you fished them sometime it might remind you of what a good time we had.” (Hemingway 96)

The passion for Bullfight can be vividly seen in the Sun Also Rises. Bill, Jake, Cohn and Mike Campbell are aficionados, and are very fervent and zealous about the Bullfight. Accordingly, they arrive at Pamplona to enjoy the fiesta of Bullfight. The youth like Cohn, Jake and Bill were flustered after experiencing the devastating effects of War. They suffer the far-

reaching but negative effects of war both physically and spiritually. Few suffer the physical injuries they get in the war, while large number of people suffers spiritually as they could not prevail over the worst effects of War. Few youngsters move from London to America as expatriates for earning living. The youth like Jake suffer from impotency and take to drinking to get rid of from the pain and suffering they experience from the war. Pierre de Coubertin, father of the modern Olympic Games, believed that sports events are very important tools for the endorsement of human rights. Pierre asserted: “Sports should have the explicit function to encourage active peace, international understanding in a spirit of mutual respect between people from different origins, Ideologies and creeds.”

The imprints of war on the minds of youth make them panicky, flaccid, alcoholic and helpless. Accordingly, they grow pessimistic and cynical in their approach towards life. The conversation of the friends such as Bill, Jake and Harris divulge the significance of fun in their life after the war. And they make fun by engaging themselves in the games and sports.

“I say, you don't know what it meant to me to have you chaps up here.”

“we have had a grand time, Harris.”

“I say, really you don't know how much it means. I've not had fun since the war.”

We'll fix together again, sometime. Don't you forget it, Harris?”

“We must. We have had such a good time”(Hemingway 95).

The passion for Bullfight is prevalent among youth like Jake, Bill and Mike. Youth often talk about Bulls and bull fighters. And those who are not fervent are not honoured. People come from far-off towns at the time of Fiesta and enjoy watching Bull fights. The hotels had the photographs of bullfighters and were framed and hung on the walls of hotels in Pamplonia. All the good bullfighters hang about at Montoya's hotel. And people who are passionate about bullfights get rooms easily and quickly. And people like Montonyo exonerate bull fighters and aficionados.

The grand celebrations of fiesta illustrate the cultural tradition of the people of Pamplonia. Author's meticulous description of the fiesta reveals the passion and enthusiasm of the people toward the sport of bull fight. “The town was getting ready for the fiesta.... The workmen put up

the gate posts that were to shut off the side streets.... Old women sweeping out the boxes”(Hemingway 111). The narrator's description of the bull fight fiesta illustrates the enthusiasm and cultural connect of the people with which they participate and enjoy the fiesta, whole heartedly. The busy and crowded streets, the horse and cattle fair plains, the wine and aguardiente shops and sellers, bull ring for bull fight, the cloth signs, flags, the crowd of peasants, and motorbuses, all give a spectacular vision to the people. The curiosity and eagerness of people with which they attended the fest also initiate enthusiasm among visitors.

The participation of peasants in the fiesta is quite notable. Peasants move into the town and get ready for the fiesta. They come from plains or hills; they reallocate their principles and get ready for fiesta. “At noon of Sunday, the 6th July, the fiesta exploded....People had been coming in all day from the country, but they were assimilated in the town. The peasants were in the outlying wine-shops. There they were drinking, getting ready for the fiesta” (Hemingway 113).

Hemingway depicts the fiesta of San Fermin, a religious fiesta. People go to the cathedral in the morning, singing and pass through the doors. The festival of fiesta also includes dancing. The dancers and musical bands, drums on the streets are noteworthy. The group of dancers, fun making, jittery, the solid lane with numerous dancers, fifers, drummers, customers, banners in their hands, and crowd are remarkable. People were full of joy; the attire of dancers is quite attractive. The fiesta continues for seven days. It also includes big religious procession. All the dignitaries civil and religious participate in the formal procession. Indians, Moors, soldiers, King and queen also participate rotating and waltzing. On the spectacle of running bulls galloping, tossing their heads up and down, people run after them enthusiastically.

Traditionally, people use sports for recreation, amusement and stress relief. The author describes that the bad weather or rain doesn't stop the fiesta. And it makes public the enthusiasm of people towards the festival. “In the wet streets, pools of water, while dancers and singers in merry making.... It was raining hard outside” (Hemingway 113).

Hemingway's sportive nature also reflects in *The Sun Also Rises*. His observations on sports, its Portrayal and his energy are a source of inspiration for the readers. Sports culture keeps

humans physically as well as spiritually strong and healthy. Moreover, sports culture across the globe leads to cultural unity and fraternity. And representation of sports and culture in the literature, improve the quality of human relations. Eventually, sports lead to betterment of the society.

Works Cited:

Bruce Emra, *Sports in Literature*, Open Access 01 Nov, 1990.

<https://typeset.io/paper/sports-in-literature-3nliv675xf> accessed on 30 september 2024.

Hemingway Ernest, *The Sun Also Rises*, Thinking I k Limited, London, 2011.

Keshar Sara, etal, *Definition of Sports Culture and its Components regarding to Experts, Athletes and Sport authorities Opinions in Man) Organizational Behaviour Management in Sport Studies* - https://fmss.journals.pnu.ac.iryarticle_3285.html?lang=en#:text.

Kumar Vinoth K, *Re Defining Sports Literature And Culture Across Genre Study*, Department of English, University of Madras, Inflibnet Centre.

<http://hdl.handle.net/10603/374588>

Olympic Charter, International Olympic Committee,2011.

2011.www.olympic.org/Documents/Olympic_Charter_en.Pdf) accessed on 29 september 2024.